

1 **Is dual-agent immunotherapy shifting the epidemiology of melanoma brain metastases? A**
2 **population-level real-world analysis and single-center validation**

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75

76

77

78 **STATEMENT OF TRANSLATIONAL RELEVANCE:**

79 This study investigates whether in patients with advanced melanoma dual-agent immunotherapy
80 (dIT), using a combination of anti-CTLA-4 and anti-PD-1, is influencing the epidemiology of
81 melanoma brain metastases (MBM) by comparing its effects to anti-CTLA4 and anti-PD1 alone.
82 Through a population-level analysis and single-center validation, the study demonstrates that dIT
83 is associated with a significantly lower incidence of MBM compared to anti-CTLA4 alone,
84 without significant differences compared to anti-PD1. Additionally, the data suggest that dIT
85 may extend overall survival (OS) and brain metastasis-free survival (BMFS) and potentially
86 offer early-phase protection against MBM development and mortality. These findings highlight
87 the potential of dIT as a primary prophylactic strategy against MBM in patients with advanced
88 melanoma, suggesting a shift in treatment paradigms. The study advocates for further
89 prospective trials to validate these results and explore the broader application of dIT in
90 preventing MBM and possibly other cancers responsive to immunotherapy.

91

92 **ABSTRACT**

93 **Background:** Melanoma brain metastases (MBM) are common in advanced melanoma and
94 linked to poor prognosis. Preventing MBM can improve survival and reduce morbidity. While
95 dual-agent immunotherapy (dIT) has improved survival, its role in MBM prevention is unclear.
96 We compared MBM incidence, overall survival (OS), and brain metastasis-free survival (BMFS)
97 between dIT and single-agent immunotherapy.

98 **Methods:** Real-world data collated from 134 organizations (TriNetX) was used to identify
99 melanoma patients without MBM at immunotherapy (IT) initiation. Patients were stratified by
100 anti-CTLA4, anti-PD1, and combo anti-CTLA4/anti-PD1 [dIT] treatment. MBM incidence was
101 measured within 5 years post-IT initiation and compared with risk ratios (RR). In a separate
102 complementary single-institution cohort, median OS and BMFS were compared between dIT,
103 anti-CTLA4, and anti-PD1 via log-rank tests and multivariate Cox proportional-hazards models.

104 **Results:** TriNetX identified 18,604 patients receiving immunotherapy (anti-CLTA4: 5,287, anti-
105 PD1: 7,923), and dIT: 5,394). MBM incidence was significantly lower in dIT (8.6%) vs. anti-
106 CTLA4 (12.2%) cohorts, (RR[95% CI], 0.72[0.61-0.86]). There was no significant difference in
107 MBM incidence between anti-PD1 (7.8%) and dIT (8.6%) (RR[95% CI], 1.13[0.93-1.36]). In the
108 single-institution analysis (n=119), 2-year OS probabilities were 90%, 80%, and 95%, and 2-year
109 BMFS probabilities were 72.7%, 80%, and 95.7%, in the dIT, anti-CTLA4, and anti-PD1
110 cohorts, respectively. DIT and anti-PD1 cohorts showed improved early-phase protection against
111 MBM development. Number of metastatic sites was significantly associated with MBM
112 development (HR 2.36; 95% CI [1.22-4.58]; p=0.01).

113 **Conclusions:** These findings highlight the impact of dIT in reducing MBM incidence,
114 suggesting it may serve as a primary prophylactic strategy. Further prospective studies are
115 warranted.

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117

118 **III. MANUSCRIPT TEXT**

119 **INTRODUCTION**

120 Melanoma is a lethal form of skin cancer with a high propensity for distant metastasis. In
121 2020, the global incidence of melanoma was roughly 325,000 new cases¹, and epidemiological
122 assessments estimate a 50% increase by 2040¹. Melanoma metastatic to the brain remains a
123 disabling cause of morbidity and mortality. Nearly 40% of stage III and IV melanoma patients
124 develop brain metastases (MBM) and this trajectory is associated with a median overall survival
125 (OS) of less than two years². Thus, there exists a pressing need not just for the treatment but also
126 for the prevention of MBM.

127 The introduction of immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICI) has changed the treatment
128 paradigm for advanced melanoma³⁻⁷. The combination of anti-programmed cell death 1 (anti-
129 PD1, e.g. nivolumab) and anti-cytotoxic T-lymphocyte 4 (anti-CTLA4, e.g. ipilimumab) agents
130 in a dual-agent immunotherapy (dIT) strategy has increased progression-free survival (PFS) by
131 nearly 9 months when compared to patients treated with anti-CTLA4 agents alone⁸. Interestingly,
132 recent clinical trials suggest that dIT also improves OS in MBM and may suffice as the sole
133 upfront intervention in those with small, asymptomatic brain lesions^{7,9,10}. Not only do ICIs
134 exhibit direct intracranial activity against existing brain lesions, but a recent meta-analysis
135 suggests that ICIs may also play a secondary preventative role in BMs, decreasing the risk of
136 additional, asynchronous lesions in existing intracranial disease¹¹.

137 We aimed to investigate if combination anti-PD1 and anti-CTLA4 immunotherapy offers
138 primary prevention against the onset of MBM, compared to anti-CTLA4 and anti-PD1 agents
139 alone. If so, we aimed to identify patient characteristics that are associated with the greatest
140 impact. The potential prophylactic role of dIT, including its early and late-phase protection, has

141 not been explored in the real-world setting at the population level nor validated with patient-level
142 data.

143

144 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

145 **Design and Reporting**

146 Two separate investigations were conducted: a population-level, real-world, database
147 analysis along with a complementary single-institution retrospective cohort study, and reported
148 using the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE)
149 guidelines.¹²

150 **Population-Level Real-World Analysis**

151 **Data Source**

152 A retrospective analysis of the TriNetX database was conducted. TriNetX Inc.
153 (Cambridge, MA) is a global health research network that consists of real-world, longitudinal
154 clinical data, collated from electronic health records (EHRs) and administrative claims data of 92
155 different healthcare organizations (HCOs) located across the United States, providing a wide
156 representation of the patient population (Please see **Supplementary Table 1** for further details).
157 For this analysis, TriNetX was superior to other large multi-institutional databases, as it allowed
158 for longitudinal patient queries; this made it possible to identify MBM incidences separately
159 from and in relation to melanoma diagnoses and treatment initiation. TriNetX offers aggregated
160 counts and statistical summaries of de-identified information and adheres to US federal law
161 Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) safeguarding healthcare data
162 privacy and security. Study exemption was granted by the Penn State Institutional Review Board
163 (IRB).

164

165 **Patient Eligibility and Data Collection**

166 Patients in TriNetX who fulfilled our inclusion criteria between June 1st, 2002, and
167 October 1st, 2019, were retrospectively queried. Codes from the *International Classification of*
168 *Diseases, Tenth Revision, Clinical Modification (ICD-10)*; Healthcare Common Procedure
169 Coding System (HCPCS); and Rx Concept Unique Identifier (RxCUI) were used. A melanoma
170 diagnosis was determined using ICD-10 code 43 and then limited to patients with no BM at
171 immunotherapy initiation. New MBM development was determined through instances of ICD-10
172 code 79.3, at least one month after initiation of IT to five years post-immunotherapy initiation.
173 Immunotherapy status was determined using both HCPCS and RxCUI codes (ipililumab: J9228,
174 1094833; nivolumab: J9299, 1597876). We opted to focus our analysis only on patients
175 receiving single-agent anti-CTLA4 and single-agent anti-PD1 versus dIT, considering that
176 patients who did not receive any IT likely had earlier stage melanoma. Patients not receiving IT
177 were excluded. Baseline demographic characteristics, comorbidities, and treatment history were
178 also collected.

179 **Data Analysis**

180 All statistical analyses were performed using the TriNetX analytics platform. Melanoma
181 patients without BM at IT initiation were stratified into three groups (1) anti-CTLA4 alone, (2)
182 anti-PD1 alone, and (3) ipilimumab and nivolumab (dIT). Raw data were analyzed using
183 descriptive statistics. Baseline covariates between treatment groups were evaluated. Unadjusted
184 Risk Ratios (RRs) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were calculated to compare MBM
185 incidences between cohorts.

186 **Single Institution Validation Study**

187 **Study Population**

188 In this single-center, retrospective cohort analysis, patients with melanoma treated with
189 IT at Penn State Health (Hershey, PA, USA) from 2012-2019 were identified. Patients aged 18
190 years or older, with pathologically confirmed melanoma who received at least one dose of either
191 combination anti-CTLA4 and anti-PD1 agents (dIT), anti-CTLA4 agent alone, or anti-PD1
192 agents alone were included. Patients with baseline brain MRIs negative for BM at the time of IT
193 initiation were included. In addition, at least 1 surveillance brain MRI scan post-immunotherapy
194 was required. Exclusion criteria were the presence of MBMs before IT initiation, MBM
195 development within one month of immunotherapy initiation, BM from a non-melanoma primary
196 tumor, and missing IT or MRI information. Additionally, patients who started IT after 2019 were
197 excluded to allow for a minimum of 3-year follow-up to evaluate the new incidence of
198 asynchronous MBMs.

199 **Data Collection**

200 EHRs of patients with melanoma treated with IT were retrospectively reviewed under an
201 IRB-approved protocol (reference number 2231). Patients with melanoma without MBMs were
202 stratified by immunotherapy type (dIT, anti-CTLA4, and anti-PD1). Demographic, clinical,
203 molecular, radiographic, treatment, and survival data were collected for each patient. To
204 minimize interobserver variability, standardized data collection tools were utilized. The presence
205 of new MBMs was recorded only if a radiology report accompanying a brain imaging study
206 confirmed the diagnosis. Patient data were collected from the date of melanoma diagnosis until
207 death or October 15, 2023, whichever occurred first. The end date was chosen to maximize the
208 follow-up period prior to data analysis.

209 **Data Analysis**

210 Patients' demographics and baseline clinical information were summarized using
211 descriptive statistics. Unadjusted comparisons between treatment groups were performed using
212 Fisher's exact test or nonparametric Wilcoxon Rank-sum test when appropriate. Time-to-event
213 outcomes were OS and brain metastasis-free survival (BMFS). OS was defined as the time from
214 the IT initiation to expiration or censoring. BMFS was defined as the time from the IT initiation
215 to the MBM or expiration. OS and BMFS survival curves were described using Kaplan-Meier
216 methods. Log-rank tests compared the survival time between groups. Multi-variable Cox
217 proportional hazard regression models were used to examine the effects of treatment and other
218 pre-selected predictors jointly. Estimated effects were quantified using hazard ratios (HR) and
219 their 95% confidence intervals (CIs). Competing risk analyses measured the cumulative
220 incidences of two competing risks: MBM only (primary event) and death without MBM
221 (competing event). The cumulative incidence functions (CIFs) were plotted by cohort. Semi-
222 parametric Fine-Gray regression model was performed to discover independent MBM risk
223 factors¹³. Early- and late-phase prevention against MBM development and mortality were
224 assessed before and after two years of IT, respectively. All analyses were performed using the
225 statistical programming language R version 4.3.2 (R Foundation for Statistical Computing,
226 Vienna, Austria). R package "cmprsk" (version 2.2-11) was used to perform competing risk
227 analysis.

228 **Data Availability**

229 Data can be made available upon request to the corresponding authors.

230

231 **RESULTS**

232 **Population-Level Real-World Analysis**

233 Collated from 134 HCOs, 8,287 melanoma patients receiving anti-CLTA4 (3,205, 39%),
234 anti-PD1 (3,218, 38.8%), and dIT with anti-CTLA4/anti-PD1 (1,864, 8.6%) were identified
235 (**Table 1, Fig. 1**). The 5-year incidences of asynchronous MBM were 12.2% in the anti-CLTA4
236 cohort, 7.8% in the anti-PD1, and 8.6% in dIT cohort. The risk of MBM development was
237 significantly lower in the dIT cohort compared to the anti-CTLA4 cohort (RR [95% CI]: 0.72
238 [0.61-0.86]). There was no significant difference in MBM development between anti-PD1 and
239 dIT cohorts (RR [95% CI]: 1.13 [0.92-1.36]).

240

241 **Single-Institution Validation Analysis**

242 **Baseline Patient Characteristics**

243 A total of 428 patients with melanoma treated with immunotherapy were identified
244 (**Table 2**). After inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied, 119 patients remained
245 (**Supplemental Fig. 1**). Of these, 54 patients were treated with dIT, 26 patients with anti-CTLA4
246 only, and 39 with anti-PD1 only. Patients were predominantly male (n=76, 63%) and White
247 (n=112, 94%). On genomic analysis, 40% had BRAF-mutant melanoma, 13.4% had NRAS
248 mutant-melanoma, and 12.6% had positive PD-L1 expression across all cohorts, with no
249 significant differences seen between cohorts. Patients had either stage III (dIT, 23.9%; anti-
250 CTLA4, 21.7%; anti-PD1, 54.3%) or stage IV (dIT, 58.9%; anti-CTLA4, 21.9%; anti-PD1,
251 19.2%) melanoma at IT initiation (p=0.0001). BRAF/MEK inhibitors were used in 70%, 23.3%,
252 and 6.7% of patients in the dIT, anti-CLTA4, and anti-PD1 cohorts, respectively (p=0.0001) after
253 immunotherapy initiation.

254 **Overall Survival and Brain Metastasis-Free Survival**

255 On multivariable Cox regression (**Fig. 2**), number of metastatic sites was significantly
256 associated with the development of BM for both stage III (HR 2.36; 95% CI [1.22-4.58]; p=0.01)
257 and stage IV melanoma (HR 1.48; 95% CI [1.11-1.96]; p=0.007)..

258 In patients with stage III melanoma, anti-PD1 treatment alone was found to be protective
259 against the development of BM (HR 0.13; 95% CI [0.02-0.95]; p=0.04).The 2-year OS
260 probability (95% CI) was 90% (75-NA), 80% (0.59-NA), and 95.7% (87.7-NA) for the dIT, anti-
261 CTLA4, and anti-PD1 cohorts, respectively. The 2-year BMFS probability (95% CI) was 72.7%
262 (75.4-100%), 80% (58.7-100%), and 95.7% (87.7-100%) for the dIT, anti-CTLA4, and anti-PD1
263 cohorts, respectively (**Fig. 3-4**). In patients with stage IV melanoma, the 2-year OS probability
264 (95% CI) was 73.6% (61.3-88.3%), 56.4% (35.2-95.1%), and 57.1% (36.3-89.9%) for the dIT,
265 anti-CTLA4, and anti-PD1 cohorts, respectively. The 2-year BMFS probability (95% CI) was
266 54.7% (41.5-72.2%), 57.5% (36.5-90.8%), and 57.1% (36.3-89.9%) for the dIT, anti-CTLA4,
267 and anti-PD1 cohorts, respectively (**Fig. 3-4**).

268 **Competing Risk Analysis**

269 On stacked cumulative incidence functions (CIF), the dIT cohort had lower MBM (29%
270 vs. 31%) and mortality (12.5% vs. 18%) compared to anti-CTLA4, respectively, at one year
271 post-immunotherapy (**Supplemental Fig. 2**). At two years post-immunotherapy, a similar trend
272 was seen, with the dIT cohort having lower death cumulative incidences (16% vs. 18%) than the
273 anti-CTLA4 cohort, however MBM incidence was higher in the dIT cohort. DIT offered better
274 early-phase (<2 years) MBM and mortality prevention compared to anti-CTLA4. There was
275 limited late-phase (>2 years) MBM and mortality prevention for both dIT and anti-CTLA4. Anti-
276 PD1 alone was associated with lower cumulative incidence of BM and death with both early-
277 phase and late-phase durability compared to both dIT and anti-CLTA4.

278

279 **Immunotherapy Treatment Patterns**

280 Combination anti-CTLA4 and anti-PD-1 dosing was prescribed in concordance with
281 recommended treatment guidelines (4 doses of each anti-CTLA4 and anti-PD-1, followed by
282 maintenance dosing of anti-PD-1 until disease progression, toxicity, or complete response
283 clinically and radiographically). Of the 54 patients treated with dIT, 40.7% completed induction
284 dosing. Treatment-related adverse events (TRAEs) occurred in 37% of patients in the dIT cohort,
285 7.7% of patients in the anti-CTLA4 cohort, and 17.9% in the anti-PD1 cohort (**Supplemental**
286 **Fig. 3, Supplemental Table 2**).

287 **DISCUSSION**

288 In this first-ever population-level real-world analysis and single-institution validation, we
289 show that dIT may decrease MBM incidence with greater clinical benefit compared to anti-
290 CTLA4, particularly in patients with stage IV melanoma. There was enhanced early-phase
291 benefit seen in the stage IV disease course over anti-PD1 and anti-CTLA4 therapy alone, which
292 is seen in both the 1- and 2-year OS and BMFS probabilities. Interestingly, in stage III patients,
293 anti-PD1 therapy alone was associated with improved OS and BMFS compared to anti-CTLA4
294 alone and even dIT, especially those with limited number of metastatic sites. Together, these data
295 support emerging clinical evidence for the role of dIT as a first-line therapy for small,
296 asymptomatic MBMs and for secondary prophylaxis against new MBMs.^{9,14} Moreover, our data
297 suggest that anti-PD1 alone may be effective for earlier stage patients with limited metastatic
298 sites over dIT or anti-CTLA4. While these findings may very well be a limitation of sample size
299 as well, we propose the hypothesis that, at the very least, anti-PD1 alone may be sufficient in a
300 single-agent strategy should any side effects develop from the combination immunotherapy.

301 Significant evidence shows dIT's superiority over anti-CTLA4 in extending survival. The
302 seminal Phase 3 CheckMate-067 trial found longer PFS (11.5 vs. 2.9 months; $p < 0.001$) and
303 higher objective response rates (57.6% vs. 19.0%, < 0.001) in dIT (N=314) compared to anti-
304 CTLA4 (N=315) in advanced melanoma *without* BM^{8,15}. The single-arm Phase 2 CheckMate-
305 204 trial (N=94) also showed dIT's substantial objective intracranial response (55%; 95% CI:
306 45-66%) in patients with small asymptomatic MBM¹⁶. Long-term trial analyses have
307 corroborated a durable 5-year response in asymptomatic MBM⁹.

308 Given its efficacy in slowing melanoma disease progression, it is hypothesized that dIT
309 can reduce the propensity for metastasis to the brain. However, data from clinical trials have yet

310 to explicitly report this outcome. Our first objective was to conduct a hypothesis-generating
311 study using real-world data (RWD), with increasing demographic, geographic, and institutional
312 patient representation, offering greater data generalizability¹⁷. Additionally, RWD allowed us to
313 account for broad practice patterns in IT administration, which is pertinent, as nearly 60% of
314 patients have grade 3 immunotherapy-related side effects that lead to early termination of
315 prescribed regimens⁸. While this data source was uniquely valuable, its shortcomings included a
316 lack of granular clinical and molecular information and difficulty in ascertaining time-to-event
317 data. Nonetheless, it offered suggestive evidence for dIT's role in the prevention of BM from
318 advanced melanoma, providing impetus for validation using more granular, patient-level data.

319 Our single-institution validation analysis enabled greater time-to-event granularity to
320 suggest that dIT prevents MBM and mortality for at least the first 2 years after starting
321 immunotherapy compared to anti-CTLA4. The lack of statistical significance is likely related to
322 the small number of patients. In the competing risk analysis, patients in the anti-CTLA4 cohort
323 had higher cumulative incidences of BM or death within the first two years compared to patients
324 in the dIT cohort. However, after 2 years, BM and death incidences were similar or greater in the
325 dIT cohort compared to the anti-CTLA4 cohort. This limited late-phase durability of dIT after
326 two years is likely multifactorial.

327 First, there was high premature treatment attrition in the dIT cohort; only 40% of patients
328 completed the full induction dosing, with majority of patients discontinuing due to TRAEs.⁸ It
329 remains unclear if induction discontinuation due to TRAEs interferes with the regimen's
330 maximal efficacy or if it is a predictor for improved outcomes. Lepper et al demonstrated that
331 immune-related adverse events (irAE) were significantly associated with longer PFS¹⁸.
332 Peripheral blood samples following immune checkpoint blockade (ICB) revealed a significant

333 reduction in circulating Tregs (CD4+, CD25+, FOXP3+ cells) in patients who developed irAEs
334 compared to those who did not. In addition, higher frequencies of CD69+CD8+ T cells and
335 CD25+CD8+ T-cells were seen in patients with irAEs compared to those without. While an
336 interesting phenomenon, these investigations have not been explicitly performed in patients with
337 MBM. Given the immune-privileged CNS, it is not yet clear if a more robust intracranial
338 immune response is seen in patients who developed irAEs after ICB. Nonetheless, our findings
339 suggest that anti-PD1 may be sufficient in a single-agent strategy and would be reasonable to
340 consider dropping the combination anti-CTLA4, should any side effects develop.

341 Second, resistance to anti-CTLA4 and anti-PD-1 agents may also be a factor in the
342 limited late-phase durability seen in our data¹⁹. In Checkmate 067, Larkin et al found nearly 55%
343 and 40% of patients with melanoma demonstrated innate resistance to anti-PD1 alone and anti-
344 CTLA4/ anti-PD1, respectively⁸. Moreover, acquired, compensatory resistance mechanisms
345 emerged within 2 years after immunotherapy initiation (25% of patients, Checkmate 067)⁸.
346 Another explanation could be due to tumor evolution, such as molecular profile changes, which
347 may require other adjuvant strategies for appropriate control²⁰. Serial CSF sampling to detect
348 circulating tumor DNA and perform next generation sequencing²¹ to identify new targetable
349 lesions or resistance biomarkers (i.e., PTEN loss¹⁹) could offer important insights for monitoring
350 and maintenance treatment.

351 Using a multi-prong approach, this is the largest study to date to investigate post-
352 immunotherapy MBM incidence. The previous largest cohort in the literature included 683
353 patients with BRAF-mutated melanoma in a multi-center retrospective study by Wang et al²².
354 Authors compared BM incidence and BMFS in patients treated with first-line immunotherapy
355 (n=266) vs. BRAF-targeted therapy (n=417). The cumulative asynchronous MBM incidence

356 following first-line immunotherapy was 16.5%²², but this was not stratified by dIT or single-
357 agent immunotherapy subgroups. On stratified sub-analyses, dIT (n=79) was associated with
358 significantly longer BMFS of 4 years compared to 1.8 and 2.4 years for patients treated with
359 ipilimumab (n=62) and nivolumab (n=125) alone, respectively²². BMFS calculated in Wang's
360 study are marginally longer than those found in the present analysis. This could be explained by
361 their patient population, which excluded those with BRAF-mutant melanoma. Roughly half of
362 our patients had BRAF-mutant melanoma and 18-36% were treated with BRAF/MEK inhibitors
363 after IT.

364 The mechanism underlying dIT's potential role in preventing MBM formation has not
365 been established; however, hypotheses can be developed based on the mechanistic understanding
366 of these two agents in combination²³⁻²⁵. First, dIT may reduce circulating tumor cells (CTCs) that
367 have intracranial seeding potential. Anti-CTLA4 sustains T-cell co-stimulation to tumor antigen-
368 presenting immune cells. This increased T-cell activation and expansion can target CTCs and
369 prevent further metastasis. Moreover, dIT may destroy seeded micrometastases, not otherwise
370 detected with standard imaging, in the brain parenchyma and TME^{26,27}. As gleaned from Tawbi
371 et al's phase 2 trial, dIT can resolve small, asymptomatic intracranial lesions^{9,16}. It is plausible
372 that dIT eradicates intracranial micrometastases through the same mechanism, preventing further
373 lesion growth, before they manifest symptomatically. Aligned with the 'seed and soil'
374 hypothesis, additional theories propose that immunotherapy may alter the genomic and
375 transcriptional profile of the brain parenchymal microenvironment, thus disrupting the 'soil' for
376 effective metastatic seeding²⁸.

377 Another frontier in melanoma treatment is the inclusion and timing of BRAF inhibitors
378 with ICB. The SECOMBIT trial is a recent three-arm, phase II randomized trial that investigated

379 the temporal relationship between dIT with anti-CTLA4 and anti-PD1 and dual-agent BRAF
380 inhibition (BRAFi) with Encorafenib and binimetinib and its impact on the development of brain
381 metastases²⁹. Interestingly, the greatest benefit in MBM prevention was seen in patients treated
382 initially with dIT followed by BRAFi, or in patients treated with dIT sandwiched between two
383 courses of BRAFi treatment. These finding further corroborate that dIT extends BMFS in
384 patients with unresectable metastatic melanoma. In light of our findings, prospective
385 investigations of BRAFi and anti-PD1 treatment temporality would be worthwhile as well³⁰.

386 This study suggests that dIT may prevent new MBM in stage IV melanoma patients, with
387 enhanced early-phase protection. These findings warrant multi-institutional, retrospective
388 validation as well as prospective investigation through international registries. Prophylactic
389 implications of dIT in other IT-responsive tumors should be explored as well³¹⁻³³. In the era of
390 precision medicine, future studies must combine clinical and molecular data to identify reliable
391 biomarkers for prognostication²¹. Finally, translational mechanistic studies should investigate
392 IT's influences on molecular or cellular soil to prevent intracranial metastatic seeding.

393 **Limitations:**

394 Our findings should be interpreted with several caveats, given their retrospective nature.
395 Most importantly, the clinician's decision to obtain brain imaging is variable and can either be
396 time-dependent, symptom-dependent, or performed for staging in the setting of relapse; the latest
397 NCCN guidelines do not support routine surveillance brain imaging in melanoma patients.
398 Surveillance imaging was not standardized across all patients, and as a result, the incidence of
399 new, asynchronous MBM may be underestimated if imaging was not obtained. Moreover, in the
400 OS analyses, our data represent pooled estimates from both asymptomatic and symptomatic
401 MBM, which likely diluted the survival responses seen between dIT, anti-CTLA4, and anti-PD1

402 cohorts. In addition, due to limitations of the database, patients could not be stratified by
403 adjuvant versus upfront ICI, however, the timeframe of inclusion serves as a surrogate to deduce
404 that majority of the patients were treated in the adjuvant setting. Finally, due to small sample
405 sizes, statistical significance was not achieved in stage-stratified OS and BMFS log-rank
406 analyses.

407

408 **Data Sharing Statement:** The data supporting the findings of this study are available upon
409 requests made to the corresponding author.

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521

522 **TABLES**

523 **Table 1.** Baseline demographic and clinical comparison of patients with malignant melanoma at
 524 the time of treatment with single- or dual-agent immunotherapy, before and after propensity
 525 score matching

Variable	Anti-CTLA4	Anti-PD1	Combo Anti-CLTA4/ Anti-PD1 (dIT)	p-value ^a	p-value ^b
Patients	3,205	3,218	1,864		
Demographics					
Age at Index	59.4 ± 14.3	61 ± 15.1	59 ± 14.2	0.36	<0.0001
Male	1,774 (60.2)	1,751 (62.6)	984 (60.1)	0.95	0.28
Female	1,153 (39.1)	973 (34.8)	607 (37.1)	0.17	0.32
Comorbidities					
Endocrine, nutritional, and metabolic diseases	1,542 (52.3)	1,588 (56.8)	1,038 (63.4)	<0.0001	0.0002
Diseases of Cardiac and Circulatory System	1,603 (54.4)	1,670 (59.7)	1,0002 (61.2)	<0.0001	0.040
Diseases of the nervous system	1,291 (43.8)	1,250 (44.7)	880 (53.8)	<0.0001	<0.0001
Injury, poisoning and certain other consequences of external causes	905 (30.7)	966 (34.5)	629 (38.4)	<0.0001	0.0008
Mental, Behavioral and Neurodevelopmental disorders	892 (30.3)	929 (33.2)	625 (38.2)	<0.0001	0.0002
Diseases of the blood and blood-forming organs and certain disorders involving the immune mechanism	760 (25.8)	781 (27.9)	567 (34.6)	<0.0001	<0.0001
Congenital malformations, deformations, and chromosomal abnormalities	171 (5.8)	194 (6.9)	134 (8.2)	0.0019	0.79
External causes of morbidity	381 (12.9)	410 (14.7)	243 (14.8)	0.69	0.79
Procedures					
Surgical Procedures on the Integumentary System	1,137 (38.6)	1,368 (0.015)	702 (42.8)	0.004	0.015
Radiation Oncology Treatment	656 (22.3)	497 (17.7)	479 (29.3)	<0.0001	<0.0001

Medications					
Pembrolizumab	276 (9.3)	222 (7.9)	325 (19.9)	<0.0001	<0.0001
Dabrafenib	185 (6.3)	159 (5.7)	207 (12.6)	<0.0001	<0.0001
Trametinib	177 (6.0)	163 (5.8)	223 (13.6)	<0.0001	<0.0001
Vemurafenib	126 (4.3)	60 (2)	76 (4.6)	0.56	0.59
Cobimetinib	37 (1.3)	40 (1.4)	55 (3.4)	<0.0001	<0.0001
MBM Incidence	391 (12.2)	253 (7.8)	165 (8.6)	0.0002	0.24
RR (95% CI)				0.72 (0.61-0.86)	1.13 (0.93-1.36)

526 **Abbreviations:** dIT=dual-agent immunotherapy; RR=Risk Ratio; CI=Confidence Interval. Bold
527 typeface= p<0.05
528 ^acomparisons between anti-CTLA4 and dIT
529 ^bcomparisons between anti-PD1 and dIT

530 **Table 2. Single-institutional** comparison of patients with malignant melanoma treated with
 531 Anti-CTLA-4, anti-PD1 or dual immunotherapy (Anti-CTLA4/Anti-PD-1) regimen.

Variable	Category	Anti-CTLA-4 N (%) = 26	Anti-PD1 N (%) = 39	Anti-CTLA4/Anti-PD-1 N (%) = 54	P-value
Sex	Male	14 (53.8)	28 (71.8)	34 (63)	0.3387
	Female	12 (46.2)	11 (28.2)	20 (37)	
Race	White	25 (96.2)	36 (92.3)	51 (94.4)	0.1989
	Black	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (3.7)	
	Other Race	1 (3.8)	0 (0)	0 (0)	
	Two or more races	0 (0)	3 (7.7%)	1 (1.9)	
Age at melanoma diagnosis	Mean (SD)	66.2 (13.7)	64.3 (14.8)	60.4 (13.7)	0.1963
	Median (range)	65 (37.7-91.1)	67.1 (25.9-85.4)	62.4 (24.5-82.9)	
Stage of melanoma at time of diagnosis	I	4 (16)	10 (27)	10 (18.9)	0.8622
	II	5 (20)	9 (24.3)	15 (28.3)	
	III	13 (52)	16 (43.2)	23 (43.4)	
	IV	3 (12)	2 (5.4)	5 (9.4)	
Number of metastatic sites (quantitative)	Mean (SD)	1.7 (1.9)	0.7 (0.8)	1.8 (1.2)	<0.0001*
	Median (range)	1 (0-6)	0 (0-3)	2 (0-5)	
NRAS mutation status	No	11 (78.6)	24 (85.7)	33 (78.6)	0.7502
	Yes	3 (21.4)	4 (14.3)	9 (21.4)	
PD-L1 expression status	No	11(84.6)	21 (75)	34 (85)	0.59
	Yes	2 (15.4)	7 (25)	6 (15)	
BRAF mutation status	No	12 (52.2)	19 (61.3)	26 (51)	0.6665

	Yes	11 (47.8)	12 (38.7)	25 (49)	
Stage of Melanoma at Immunotherapy start	III	10 (38.5)	25 (64.1)	11 (20.4)	0.0001*
	IV	16 (61.5)	14 (35.9)	43 (79.6)	
BRAF Inhibitor Use	No	19 (73.1)	37 (94.9)	33 (61.1)	0.0004*
	Yes	7 (26.9)	2 (5.1)	21 (38.9)	

532 **Abbreviations:** Bold typeface= p<0.05

533

534

535 **FIGURES**

536 **Figure 1.** 5-year Incidence of New, Asynchronous Melanoma Brain Metastasis, Stratified by
537 Immunotherapy Treatment.

538 Abbreviations: IT=Immunotherapy

539 **Figure 2.** Multi-variable Cox proportional hazards regression model identifies prognosticators
540 for brain metastasis development in (A) stage III and (B) stage IV melanoma patients treated
541 with immunotherapy.

542 Abbreviations: BM=Brain Metastasis

543 **Figure 3.** Overall survival (OS) probability for A. Stage III and B. Stage IV melanoma patients
544 treated with immunotherapy.

545 **Figure 4.** Brain metastasis free survival (BMFS) probability for A. Stage III and B. Stage IV
546 melanoma patients treated with immunotherapy.

547 **Supplemental Figure 1.** Single-institution patient cohort selection per inclusion/exclusion
548 criteria. Abbreviations: IT=Immunotherapy; BM=Brain metastasis.

549 **Supplemental Figure 2.** Competing risk analysis with stacked cumulative incidences of brain
550 metastasis and mortality, from immunotherapy initiation. Abbreviations: BM=Brain metastasis.

551 **Supplemental Figure 3.** Combination Immunotherapy Induction Completion, A. number of
552 induction doses received, and B. treatment-related adverse events due to drug toxicity.

553 Abbreviations: IT=Immunotherapy.

5-year Incidence of New Asynchronous Melanoma Brain Metastasis, Stratified by Immunotherapy Type

A Stage III Patients

B Stage IV Patients

A Stage III Patients

B Stage IV Patients

A Stage III Patients

Treatment group	Number at risk										
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Anti-CTLA4 Cohort	10	8	8	8	7	7	5	4	1	1	0
Combo Anti-CTLA4/Anti-PD1 Cohort	11	9	8	6	4	2	1	0	0	0	0
Anti-PD1 Cohort	25	22	21	19	14	8	3	0	0	0	0

B Stage IV Patients

Treatment group	Number at risk										
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Anti-CTLA4 Cohort	16	8	7	5	5	5	5	5	5	3	2
Combo Anti-CTLA4/Anti-PD1 Cohort	43	27	22	20	14	12	9	5	2	1	0
Anti-PD1 Cohort	14	9	8	6	5	5	4	1	0	0	0

Melanoma Patients treated with Immunotherapy at Single Institution
N=428

Excluded
BM on or before IT (n=78)
Stage I or II at IT initiation (n=75)
Non-Melanoma pathology (n=28)
BM from other primary (n=2)
Incomplete IT data (n=76)
Missing baseline negative MRI at time of IT initiation (n=50)

Melanoma Patients on Immunotherapy who met inclusion criteria
N=119

**Combo
Anti-CTLA4 + Anti-PD1**
N=54

**Single
Anti-CTLA4**
N=26

**Single
Anti-PD1**
N=39

A. Number of Dual IT Induction Doses Received

B. Immunotherapy Toxicity Incidence

